

B1/IS washed erythrocytes

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 238 nm
1.21e+9	233	Modal diameter 235 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 308 nm
		D50 233 nm
		D10 161 nm
		Standard deviation 73 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 22 /frame
Tracked particles: 322

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 93

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 25.8
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.874

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 11:58:05 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:01:49

B2/IS isolate from plasma

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	267 nm
		Modal diameter	165 nm
1.85e+9	231	D90	440 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	231 nm
		D10	159 nm
		Standard deviation	123 nm

Number of videos: 7
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 28 /frame
Tracked particles: 320

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 84

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 26.0
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.870

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 12:05:58 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:08:16

B3/SN supernatant from plasma

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	161 nm
		Modal diameter	125 nm
1.42e+9	137	D90	246 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	137 nm
		D10	97 nm
		Standard deviation	81 nm

Number of videos: 9
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 30 /frame
Tracked particles: 333

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION
 Particles to track (minimum): 300
 Max number of videos: 10
 Number of frames: 100
 Averaging frames: 100
 Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS
 Intensity (%): 86

DETECTION
 Threshold: 4.20

Macro particles
 Minimum radius: 10
 Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
 Temperature (°C): 26.0
 Use water viscosity: yes
 Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.870

Institution: Q4
 Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
 Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
 Operator: MYRIADE
 Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 12:13:00 - UTC+2
 End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:15:59

B4/SN supernatant from centrifugation of PBS suspension of plasma EPs

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	235 nm
		Modal diameter	175 nm
1.35e+9	206	D90	379 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	206 nm
		D10	117 nm
		Standard deviation	113 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 22 /frame
Tracked particles: 305

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 85

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 26.2
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.866

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 12:17:00 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:19:59

B5/IS isolate from suspension of aged washed erythrocytes

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	219 nm
		Modal diameter	205 nm
3.49e+9	212	D90	295 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	212 nm
		D10	157 nm
		Standard deviation	55 nm

Number of videos: 4
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 58 /frame
Tracked particles: 381

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 84

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 26.2
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.866

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 12:24:45 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:26:22

B8/IS isolate from suspension of aged washed erythrocytes

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 255 nm
3.37e+9	238	Modal diameter 225 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 339 nm
		D50 238 nm
		D10 181 nm
		Standard deviation 80 nm

Number of videos: 4
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 50 /frame
Tracked particles: 350

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 83

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 26.3
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.864

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 12:36:50 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 12:39:47

S1/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter -
5.83e+7	-	Modal diameter -
part/mL	nm	D90 -
		D50 -
		D10 -
		Standard deviation -

Number of videos: 1
Saturation: 94%

Average counted particles: 3 /frame
Tracked particles: 0

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition has been stopped by operator.
[MANUFACTURER] Data too scarce for complete characterisation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 85	Temperature (°C): 26.9
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.853
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 13:58:47 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:00:21

S6/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter -
4.75e+7	-	Modal diameter -
part/mL	nm	D90 -
		D50 -
		D10 -
		Standard deviation -

Number of videos: 1 Average counted particles: 3 /frame
 Saturation: 94% Tracked particles: 0

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition has been stopped by operator.
 [MANUFACTURER] Data too scarce for complete characterisation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 85	Temperature (°C): 26.9
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.853
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
 Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
 Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
 Operator: MYRIADE
 Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:00:49 - UTC+2
 End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:01:54

S9/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	271 nm
		Modal diameter	190 nm
2.82e+8	213	D90	409 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	213 nm
		D10	146 nm
		Standard deviation	159 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 6 /frame
Tracked particles: 61

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 92	Temperature (°C): 26.9
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.853
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:03:03 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:06:40

S11/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter -
6.79e+8	649	Modal diameter -
part/mL	nm	D90 -
		D50 649 nm
		D10 -
		Standard deviation -

Number of videos: 1
Saturation: 97%

Average counted particles: 20 /frame
Tracked particles: 9

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition has been stopped by operator.
[MANUFACTURER] Data too scarce for complete characterisation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 87	Temperature (°C): 27.0
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.851
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:09:49 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:11:44

S12/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter -
5.60e+7	-	Modal diameter -
part/mL	nm	D90 -
		D50 -
		D10 -
		Standard deviation -

Number of videos: 2 Average counted particles: 3 /frame
 Saturation: 93% Tracked particles: 0

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition has been stopped by operator.
 [MANUFACTURER] Data too scarce for complete characterisation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 83	Temperature (°C): 27.0
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.851
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
 Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
 Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
 Operator: MYRIADE
 Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:13:12 - UTC+2
 End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:17:24

S13/IS isolate from spruce needle homogenate

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter -
1.34e+8	786	Modal diameter -
part/mL	nm	D90 -
		D50 786 nm
		D10 -
		Standard deviation -

Number of videos: 1 Average counted particles: 4 /frame
 Saturation: 90% Tracked particles: 1

Comments:

*[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition has been stopped by operator.
 [MANUFACTURER] Data too scarce for complete characterisation.*

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 91	Temperature (°C): 27.0
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.851
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
 Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
 Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
 Operator: MYRIADE
 Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:17:35 - UTC+2
 End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:19:04

T1/IS isolate from suspension of flagellae of Tetraselmis chuii microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	284 nm
		Modal diameter	175 nm
9.61e+8	235	D90	490 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	235 nm
		D10	145 nm
		Standard deviation	157 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 22 /frame
Tracked particles: 184

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 83	Temperature (°C): 27.0
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.851
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:19:59 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:23:35

P3/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 424 nm
6.26e+8	387	Modal diameter 350 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 721 nm
		D50 387 nm
		D10 198 nm
		Standard deviation 200 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 13 /frame
Tracked particles: 192

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.
[MANUFACTURER] 8 videos with non-optimal saturation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 77	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:24:51 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:29:46

P4/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 459 nm
4.04e+8	389	Modal diameter 390 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 833 nm
		D50 389 nm
		D10 173 nm
		Standard deviation 252 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 88%

Average counted particles: 9 /frame
Tracked particles: 101

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.
[MANUFACTURER] 7 videos with non-optimal saturation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 66	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:31:22 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:37:42

P11/SN supernatant from ultracentrifugation of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	494 nm
		Modal diameter	390 nm
2.09e+8	398	D90	873 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	398 nm
		D10	210 nm
		Standard deviation	253 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 5 /frame
Tracked particles: 40

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 82	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:39:11 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:42:12

P12/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	313 nm
		Modal diameter	150 nm
3.10e+8	294	D90	538 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	294 nm
		D10	112 nm
		Standard deviation	187 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 7 /frame
Tracked particles: 51

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 82	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:43:28 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:46:26

P16/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 436 nm
		Modal diameter 330 nm
5.11e+8	387	D90 814 nm
part/mL	nm	D50 387 nm
		D10 178 nm
		Standard deviation 227 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 91%

Average counted particles: 11 /frame
Tracked particles: 166

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.
[MANUFACTURER] 7 videos with non-optimal saturation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 77	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:47:04 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:50:13

P21/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 331 nm
		Modal diameter 230 nm
3.45e+8	286	D90 588 nm
part/mL	nm	D50 286 nm
		D10 150 nm
		Standard deviation 197 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 7 /frame
Tracked particles: 70

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 81	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:51:05 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:54:30

P26/IS isolate from conditioned culture media of Phaeodactylum tricornutum microalgae

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	413 nm
		Modal diameter	230 nm
2.45e+8	334	D90	824 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	334 nm
		D10	199 nm
		Standard deviation	244 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 6 /frame
Tracked particles: 51

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.
[MANUFACTURER] 3 videos with non-optimal saturation.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 83	Temperature (°C): 27.2
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:54:58 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:58:00

LA-1000 liposomes diluted 1000x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 321 nm
1.94e+9	303	Modal diameter 295 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 465 nm
		D50 303 nm
		D10 192 nm
		Standard deviation 119 nm

Number of videos: 8
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 29 /frame
Tracked particles: 329

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 83

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20

Macro particles

Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 27.2
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.847

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:38:36 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:42:53

LB-1000 liposomes diluted 1000x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 313 nm
4.94e+8	294	Modal diameter 270 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 455 nm
		D50 294 nm
		D10 172 nm
		Standard deviation 119 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 9 /frame
Tracked particles: 96

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 82

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 27.3
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.845

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:56:06 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:59:03

LC-1000 liposomes diluted 1000x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 301 nm
7.45e+8	273	Modal diameter 195 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 441 nm
		D50 273 nm
		D10 185 nm
		Standard deviation 110 nm

Number of videos: 10
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 11 /frame
Tracked particles: 138

Comments:

[MANUFACTURER] Acquisition stopped because maximum number of videos reached.

Settings:

ACQUISITION	LED SETTINGS	PHYSICAL CONSTANTS
Particles to track (minimum): 300	Intensity (%): 82	Temperature (°C): 27.3
Max number of videos: 10		Use water viscosity: yes
Number of frames: 100	DETECTION	Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.845
Averaging frames: 100	Threshold: 4.20	
Exposure time (ms): 0.90	Macro particles	
	Minimum radius: 10	
	Minimum hot pixels: 80	

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:11:30 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:14:22

LA-100 liposomes diluted 100x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 312 nm
5.51e+9	296	Modal diameter 235 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 454 nm
		D50 296 nm
		D10 193 nm
		Standard deviation 108 nm

Number of videos: 3
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 79 /frame
Tracked particles: 403

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 83

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20

Macro particles

Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 27.3
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.845

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 14:50:27 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 14:51:42

LB-100 liposomes diluted 100x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter	315 nm
		Modal diameter	255 nm
3.91e+9	286	D90	468 nm
part/mL	nm	D50	286 nm
		D10	198 nm
		Standard deviation	123 nm

Number of videos: 4
Saturation: 92%

Average counted particles: 55 /frame
Tracked particles: 342

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 82

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20

Macro particles

Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 27.3
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.845

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:07:00 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:08:47

LC-100 liposomes diluted 100x

Concentration	Median diameter	Mean diameter 326 nm
5.30e+9	304	Modal diameter 275 nm
part/mL	nm	D90 480 nm
		D50 304 nm
		D10 194 nm
		Standard deviation 128 nm

Number of videos: 3
Saturation: 93%

Average counted particles: 75 /frame
Tracked particles: 371

Comments:

Settings:

ACQUISITION

Particles to track (minimum): 300
Max number of videos: 10
Number of frames: 100
Averaging frames: 100
Exposure time (ms): 0.90

LED SETTINGS

Intensity (%): 82

DETECTION

Threshold: 4.20
Macro particles
Minimum radius: 10
Minimum hot pixels: 80

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Temperature (°C): 27.3
Use water viscosity: yes
Viscosity (mPa.s): 0.845

Institution: Q4
Serial number: VD1-1911-0005
Software version: qvir: 2.6.0.7378
Operator: MYRIADE
Begin date: 23.08.2022 - 15:15:31 - UTC+2
End date: 23.08.2022 - 15:22:06